

Deliverable D3.3 Single entry-point portal for the toolkit for all stakeholders

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Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
2022-11-02	0v1	Rob Hoof (DTL-Projects)	Initial version
2023-01-18	0v2	Rob Hoof (DTL-Projects)	Sent to PMU after incorporating internal WP feedback
2023-01-20	0v3	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission
08/03/2023	0v4	Rob Hoof (DTL-Projects)	MB comments addressed
08/03/2023	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

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1. Executive Summary

We have developed a single point of entry to information, guidelines and best practices for data management in life sciences. This is established as three interconnected resources that cater for different aspects covering the requirements of the diverse stakeholders (researchers, data stewards, and funders and policy makers).

The work focussed on establishing the interconnections between the resources. We implemented technologies to facilitate making and maintaining these connections, contributing to long-term sustainability. Both in RDMkit as in the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW), new features were introduced to make this possible. We collaborated with FAIR Cookbook, from the IMI FAIRPlus project, to also integrate this resource. While RDMkit provides guidelines and broader context, DSW allows users to drill down on a specific topic using questionnaires. FAIR Cookbook brings together detailed recipes to do specific tasks, related to making data FAIR. These three resources are therefore complementary and provide the diverse stakeholders with appropriate information tailored to their needs.

To establish the integrations, we have collaborated across work packages in ELIXIR-CONVERGE, and worked with other projects such as IMI FAIRPlus.

This work enabled us to provide users access to research data management resources through a single point of entry.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	Yes
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	No
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising	Yes

all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	No
Key Result 3.4: Enable 'FAIR at source' practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	Yes
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	No

3. Introduction

3.1 Deliverable scope

The scope of this deliverable is to provide a single entry-point portal for the toolkit for all stakeholders. In this deliverable we describe how we have worked on integrating ELIXIR RDM related resources with RDMkit in order to show a body of knowledge with entry points for different users and use cases .

The toolkit (RDMkit) for research data management provides best practices and guidelines in the forms of text articles, links to nested questionnaires (in DSW) and practical recipes (in FAIR Cookbook, product of the FAIRPlus project). These three resources are therefore complementary, addressing different viewpoints or requirements of the end users. All three resources provide

different ways to access RDM knowledge, generated within ELIXIR by CONVERGE and other projects, for different stakeholders.

Since the content of the three resources is thoroughly interconnected, each single resource could also be an entry-point portal to reach the other two resources. However, RDMkit, developed fully within this project, provides the most general content, therefore it is de facto the main entry point to guide stakeholders through RDM information following the general-to-specific method or order. Nevertheless, the three ELIXIR resources for RDM guidelines have been placed in a dedicated section (“Guidelines”) in the ELIXIR Europe website (under “What we offer”) to be more visible for the users of the ELIXIR services, which can then choose the best entry point for their use cases.

3.2 Relationship with other WPs

Descriptive best practices and guidelines about common data management tasks have been provided by WP1 (DM Network) and domain-specific ones by WP5 (demonstrators) and WP8 (Covid-19 data portal). Additional domain specific guidelines have been provided with the collaboration of some ELIXIR communities (see *Your domain* section in RDMkit). The toolkit links out to ELIXIR registries, such as TeSS, FAIRsharing and bio.tools, to point the readers to available training materials, policies, standards, databases and software tools related to a specific task or context. The linking to registries has been done in collaboration with WP2 for TeSS and with members of the ELIXIR interoperability platform for FAIRsharing and bio.tools.

A collaboration with WP4 and the outreach/communication team at ELIXIR Hub resulted in the “Guideline” section of the ELIXIR Europe website, as part of “What we offer”, presenting RDMkit and the integrated resources, DSW and FAIR Cookbook, to the visitors of the ELIXIR website.

3.2 Methodology to be applied

It has been clear from the start that there are different types of audiences for RDM knowledge. During CONVERGE, we defined the main stakeholders as follows:

- *Researchers* primarily focused on the science or scientific results, that need to perform data management tasks during a research project
- *Data stewards* focused on supporting researchers or performing data management tasks
- *Infrastructure or services providers* that make and maintain technical infrastructures for data stewards and researchers
- *Funders and policy makers* that make policies, evaluate DMPs and fund infrastructure providers.

While making a single entry-point portal for the toolkit for all stakeholders, several aspects needed to be taken into account:

- The role of data stewards and their tasks are broad and not yet defined consistently across institutions and countries, so there is a need to disseminate the definition of this role and learning paths.
- Tasks that are performed by data stewards in some institutions are often carried out by Principal investigators, research software engineers, bioinformaticians, librarians, IT and other departments in other institutions, because the data steward role has not yet been adopted or the data management responsibilities are distributed differently.

- Useful guidelines for data management can be general and applicable across domains, tools and institutions only to a certain extent, therefore domain, tool or institution specific information is necessary.
- Given the variety of the infrastructure for data management in different countries, describing examples of how others have implemented data management practices will be an effective communication strategy.

Based on these observations, the entry-point portal for the toolkit for all stakeholders needed to guide a heterogeneous group of readers based on the answers they could be looking for in RDMkit.

Therefore, the approach of having different views for different stakeholders (or persona) was discarded and it was decided to make clear what kind of content or answers the readers should expect to find in each RDMkit section and to invest in the search bar for free text search. A tagging-based system was implemented to group pages, tools and resources based on data life cycle stages, roles, domains, tasks, tool assemblies and countries, to facilitate discovery of relevant information.

RDMkit and its integrations (DSW, FAIR Cookbook) needed to be made visible for the users of the ELIXIR services. A clear explanation about the scope and the content of each resource was essential to guide the users towards the best entry-point for their use case.

As described in D3.1 (Assembled Starter Toolkit), WP3 started by creating a simple structure to collect the knowledge that was available in the ELIXIR network (e.g. by involving people from the RDM network in WP1, with training and capacity building expertise in WP2, and with specific disciplinary sub-fields of the life sciences through WP5). This resulted in the content of RDMkit that has in the meantime proven its value in many places. The RDMkit technical infrastructure was formalised in a Jekyll theme (named *ELIXIR Toolkit theme*, ETT) to ease the maintenance and increase sustainability and impact.

Task 3.3 in CONVERGE is to integrate RDMkit with DSW and with other ELIXIR resources, TeSS, bio.tools, FAIRsharing and other relevant resources for RDM. To achieve that we implement integrations that make use of existing APIs of DSW, of a link discovery utility based on the identifiers of tools for bio.tools and FAIRSharing, and of manual curation (WP2) of the annotations in TeSS. Although it was not the main scope of the project, we also put in place a process based on a central YAML file under ELIXIR Europe GitHub repository to list RDMkit and FAIRCookbook cross references; a joint editorial board manage the cross reference between the two resources.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Integration of RDMkit with Data Stewardship Wizard

The integration between RDMkit and Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) has taken two paths. First, the tools on both sides, both RDMkit and DSW, have been adapted:

- It has been made possible in DSW to navigate around in a questionnaire without having created a project before. In addition, so-called “deep links” facilitate the direct access of any particular section of the knowledge model through an external link. Together, these two features make links to specific places in the knowledge model from RDMkit possible.

- In RDMkit, a feature was implemented to link from any page directly to a corresponding section in the DSW knowledge model, and to render these links in a recognizable box. An automated weekly process was set up that scans the DSW knowledge model, and harvests any links from DSW to RDMkit. Each link is reversed and added at the appropriate place in RDMkit. This approach ensures the resources remain in sync.

After the technology was in place, to define the appropriate links 11 workshops were held in which experts on the DSW and subject matter experts from RDMkit (seeded from the author lists of relevant pages in RDMkit) came together for 2 hours, and discussed a particular subset of information from RDMkit and the corresponding sections of the knowledge model in DSW. Initially topics were selected in order of priority from the data life cycle; later specific topics were selected based on priorities selected by the editors involved in specific RDMkit pages like Human Data and the different use cases in WP5 of the ELIXIR Converge project. During the workshops links were immediately added to the DSW knowledge model, and notes were taken to document actions that could be taken to improve the content of the RDMkit pages. Each workshop started with a demonstration of the process of editing a knowledge model; this process evolved a lot over the period of this part of the CONVERGE project, not in the least based on feedback and experience obtained from the practical application in these workshops. Most of the work in the workshops consisted of actually encoding the knowledge that was described in “considerations”-sections in RDMkit pages in the form of actionable decision trees which were encoded in the DSW knowledge model. These decision trees can help researchers and data stewards who need a little more guidance to choose between the different options given in RDMkit; technically they will be guided to the appropriate DSW knowledge model corner by an automatically reversed deep link represented visually recognizable in the appropriate RDMkit page.

Table 1: Workshop events that were organised in order to improve interlinking content between RDMkit and the Data Stewardship Wizard core knowledge model.

#	Date	Topic
1	2021-10-29	Data Sharing
2	2021-11-30	Collecting Data
3	2021-12-14	Data Processing
4	2022-01-11	Human Data
5	2022-02-03	Data Preservation
6	2022-02-11	Plant Science
7	2022-02-15	Data Analysis
8	2022-03-08	Data Reuse
9	2022-04-12	Toxicology
10	2022-05-13	Biomolecular Simulation

11	2022-06-14	Epitranscriptomics Data
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4.2 Integration of RDMkit with FAIR Cookbook

In the FAIRplus project, practical experience with making data from IMI projects FAIR was written up in FAIR Recipes. These are available at <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/home.html>

Just like for the interlinking of DS Wizard and RDMkit, the interlinking of RDMkit with FAIR Cookbook has consisted of a combination of technical and content aspects.

For the technical coupling it was decided to make a central, commonly maintained document, in yaml format, under version control to describe the pairwise linking between individual recipes in the cookbook and individual pages in RDMkit. Both FAIR Cookbook and RDMkit software implementations were modified to query this document on a weekly basis, and fully automatically and consistently maintain the links between the resources. Automations were put in place to increase sustainability of this linkage document. This includes the automated updating of the titles so they never get out of sync and the automatic opening of issues each time new content is added to one of the resources. The latter one is used to identify if new links need to be created in the linking document.

As both resources source content from a broad community, to address content, a combined editorial board was created with members from both RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook editorial boards, meeting every month. In meetings of the combined editorial boards the merit of individual inter-project links can be discussed. Between editorial board meetings, suggested changes to the linking document are reviewed by at least one editor of each resource for approval.

The joint RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook editorial board organised a BioHackathon project in 2022 in order to create user journeys through the ELIXIR resources for RDM guidelines.

4.3 Entry to the knowledge resources on the ELIXIR Web site

In order to make the integration between RDMkit and the other RDM related ELIXIR resources (DSW and FAIR Cookbook) explicit, a single page on the ELIXIR web site was created that is pointing out all RDM resources at <https://elixir-europe.org/what-we-offer/guidelines>.

5. Results

The crosslinks between the three RDM resources, RDMkit, Data Stewardship Wizard and FAIR Cookbook (see also Figure 1 and Figure 2) make it possible for users of any one of the three to explore the information as if they formed a single resource; with a user which is progressing between different phases in planning or executing data management for a research project possibly using more of one resource in one phase of the process and more of another of the three resources when reaching another phase in the project. Through the integrations, the three resources can be used as a single resource by the user.

Figure 1: Crosslinks between RDMkit and Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW).

Figure 2: Crosslinks between RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook.

A single page on the ELIXIR web site links to each of the three resources, bringing them truly together in a single place (Figure 3). The three ELIXIR resources for RDM guidelines have been placed in a dedicated section (“Guidelines”) in the ELIXIR Europe website (under “What we offer”) to be more visible for the users of the ELIXIR services, which can then choose the best entry point for their use

cases. The users' choice about where to start to address their question or use case it will be based on the description of each resource provided on the ELIXIR website:

- RDMkit for general best practices and guidelines, examples and for pointers to more specific/hands-on resources.
- DSW for detailed and interactive guidance when making a DMP
- FAIR Cookbook for step-by-step protocols on how to implement FAIR in practice by using specific software or standards and tools.

Figure 3: Single entry point on the ELIXIR web site.

In the process of realising this goal, significant improvements have been made to the content of at least RDMkit (see D1.4) and the Data Stewardship Wizard core knowledge model.

Thanks to the synergic improvements implemented in the three resources, the users of ELIXIR services can find RDM guidelines on ELIXIR website and then choose where to start based on the type of question they are trying to answer. After the users have chosen an entry-point, they will promptly see the connections with the other two resources, where appropriate, and will be able to navigate all the resources as one. Moreover, the users will be able to easily reach registries (FAIRsharing, bio.tools, TeSS), tools and resources (e.g., BioSchemas, Deposition databases, etc) relevant for RDM topics from each resource, after they have been given the right context for their use in RDM.

6. Conclusions

Through the efforts described in this deliverable, data stewards and researchers looking for research data management information can now make use of RDMkit, Data Stewardship Wizard and FAIR Cookbook as if it was a single information resource. A lightweight governance model for changes makes it possible to maintain the consistency of this virtual resource over time.

7. Impact

The result of this work has created a serious step in the direction of **increased research efficiency**: through more easily accessible good practice information as well as through better findability of ELIXIR-maintained technical solutions for data stewardship. At the same time, smaller contributions to the desired ELIXIR impact classes of **relationship capital** and **RI sustainability** have been made.

8. Next Steps

RDMkit, Data Stewardship Wizard and the FAIR Cookbook will each continue working on serving their own target user group. The approaches developed and technologies implemented in this part of the project will make sure that such continued development will benefit the users of all three. It is the intention to maintain the development of these resources from a new ELIXIR Community for Data Management practice.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable.

